

DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL INFLUENCING SKILLS OF YOUNG ACADEMIC ENGINEERS – CASE: YOUNG PROFESSIONALS' FORUM (YPF)

J. Ylitalo¹

University Lecturer

Aalto University

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management

T. Kostamo

Doctoral Student

Aalto University

Department of Industrial Engineering and Management

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ABSTRACT

Professional working life skills have become an essential part of the engineering skillset in recent years. However, it seems that basic engineering education does not sufficiently provide the students with these skills. The Finnish Association of Academic Engineers and Architects (TEK) established a new kind of peer forum to develop these skills of its younger members. The forum consists of workshops, assignments, and peer dialogues over a four-month time period. The forum's approach leans on a dialogic, experiential and reflective way of learning enabling the participants to further build their personal influencing practices; investigate their professional relationships; experiment changes in their self-management practices; and share their experiences in peer groups. Since 2017, over 900 young TEK members have participated. The aim of this study in progress is to make an overview to the experienced impacts of the forum and scrutinize the forum's influence mechanisms in a more detailed way. The data was collected through an inquiry to all participants. The study indicates that the forum has been most influential in supporting the participants to become more aware of their professional influence, to build capabilities to change their personal and social practices, and to enhance their professional networks. The most significant impact element has been various peer discussions and dialogues. As a conclusion the study highlights the needs and interests of young professionals to develop the essential working life skills.

¹ J. Ylitalo

jari.ylitalo@aalto.fi

1 INTRODUCTION

Professional working life skills have become an essential part of engineering skillset. The general change of working life to dynamically evolving VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity) environment and the new forms of organizing require more advanced competences in communication, collaboration, personal and professional influencing as well as in change and development from all professionals including engineers [1,2]. However, it seems that basic engineering education provides the students insufficiently with these skills [3].

As a part of the service offering to its younger members TEK (Association of Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland) initiated a new peer forum to support the development of personal and professional influencing skills of freshly graduated academic engineers. The aim of this study is to make an overview of the experienced and perceived impacts of the forum, and highlight the influence mechanisms of the forum in more detailed way. The research questions are: 1) *What have been the experienced impacts from the Young Professionals' Forum?* 2) *What have been the most essential elements of the forum on behalf of the impacts?*

2 YOUNG PROFESSIONALS' FORUM (YPF)

TEK (The Association of Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland) has some 77000 members of which 20000 are student members. TEK along with most of the professional associations in Finland has suffered a declining number of members during the past decade. After graduation, a growing number of student members has discontinued their memberships. To respond this negative trend TEK has renewed its strategy and started to develop services and activity models that would better serve the needs of its younger members. The new strategy has been successful and TEK has been able to turn the trend to positive. The Young Professionals' Forum (YPF) has been one of these responses. However, an even more fundamental motivation for the forum has been to support the young engineers to develop their essential working life skills in their early careers.

As leadership teachers we (the authors) were invited to develop the pilot version of the forum. The pilot version was arranged in 2017 with 50 participants. The positive feedback encouraged to continue the service. Since 2017 the forum has been arranged fifteen times for over 900 participants. In practice the forum is four-month long training process consisting of four three-hour workshops, three personal assignments, and three peer group meetings between the workshops. Next the pedagogical foundation and practical design of the YPF will be presented more in detail.

2.1 Pedagogical foundation

The pedagogical foundation of the forum is based on constructivist and experiential learning with dialogic, reflective, reflexive, and even critical undertones [4,5]. Improving personal influencing skills and practices in a sustainable way is a highly personal process as we all have a unique growth history, personalities, strengths and

developmental needs, learning abilities, and professional contexts. Influencing skills are grounded on our views of social reality, our values, our past experiences, and our routinized habits and practices. Thus, improving personal influencing skills in a sustained way requires *1) willingness to scrutinize the prevalent personal beliefs, principles and values, influencing requirements within own professional context, and current personal and social practices, 2) getting experience of improvement steps in personal practices and reflecting on the experiences, and 3) to repeat the new practices long enough to routinize them.*

The additional elements of the learning process are processuality, contextuality, and a facilitative way of instructing. *Processuality* refers to the duration and rhythm of the process as well as the integration, iteration and reciprocity of different program elements, themes, and concepts. *Contextuality* refers to the connection to each participants own professional and personal life context as well as to the temporary learning community formed in the forum. *A facilitative way of instructing* means that the role of the instructors is to engage the participants in an active conversational process and sharing right from the start; to enable allowing, trusting, and open atmosphere; to provide the participants with appropriate concepts and theories; and to maintain adequate structure of the process.

2.2 Practical application – forum design and delivery

The forum has been arranged mainly in the Helsinki area where the majority of TEK members live but few times also in other major Finnish cities. Due to COVID19 pandemic the forum was turned to online mode, which at first was worrying as the forum's concept leans heavily on living face-to-face conversations. Despite our worries the online forum seemed to serve its purpose relatively well. The online mode enabled participants to join more easily from distant locations. All in all the number of single forum participants has varied from 30 up to one hundred.

Basically the Young Professionals' Forum is a four-month long personal and social learning process consisting of four three-hour workshops, three individual assignments and three peer group meetings between the workshops. The aims of the forum are to *1) support newly graduated engineers to develop their personal professional influence and self-management, 2) strengthen participants' ability to build and develop their professional relationships and interaction, 3) build practices and commitment for continuous development as an interactor and influencer, and 4) enable participants to build and strengthen their professional identities further.*

The forum is strongly participant-focused and is planned to create a holistic learning process, in which different elements build on each other. The participants are requested to investigate and scrutinize their current working practices, professional relationships, leadership thinking and preassumptions, interview their collaboration partners and ask personal feedback, and experience small step changes in their professional practices. These experiences are discussed and shared in the workshops, in which appropriate concepts and supportive tools are also introduced by the facilitators. Furthermore, in the beginning of the process the participants are

divided into peer groups which aims to serve as support groups throughout the whole process. The peer groups meet between the workshops and share the assignment experiences as well as discuss the topics that are relevant for the group.

The participants are asked to document their assignments but they are allowed choose the level and accuracy of the documentation as the purpose is most of all to serve the personal learning. Documentation through writing allows the participants to reflect on the experiences in a profound way. The assignments build on each other forming a holistic review of the personal state of the art situation. The final report forms a reference point for assesment of personal development and thus, at its best serves as a reflective framework for further development.

3 METHODOLOGY

An online inquiry was sent to 740 former YPF participants. 123 responded to the questionnaire. The questionnaire contained five background questions, ten scale (quantitative) questions, and three open (qualitative) questions. The inquiry aimed at charting the initial participation motivation and expectations, the experienced and perceived impacts, the most influential elements of the forum, and the hidden potential of the forum. The qualitative data was analyzed following the guidelines of qualitative content analysis.

4 FINDINGS

The findings are divided into three sections. First the background of the respondents is summarized. Second the expressed impacts and usefulness of the forum are presented based on the questionnaire data. Finally, the impact factors of the YPF are presented based on the open questions of the inquiry.

4.1 Background of the respondents

The YPF has been arranged fifteen times from 2017 on. There were respondents quite evenly from all the years the forum has been arranged. The YPF participants represent in practice all possible industries and engineering fields as the TEK is an association for all academic engineers and architects. The YPF is directed to freshly graduated professionals (less than five years from the graduation) thus the vast majority of them fit to age range from 25 to 35. During the forum 90% of the respondents were in specialist roles and 10% in managerial roles.

To gain learning benefits from the forum based heavily on the participants' own activity requiring to use of their free time to the workshops and assignments, and daring to share their personal thoughts and experiences with others. The respondents were asked how the overall way of working suited to them (*"The way the forum was organised was successful for me"*). 68% of the respondents expressed that the way of working suited to them well or very well. For 17% the way of working was ok, and for 15% less suitable. Furthermore, the respondents were also asked to evaluate how pleased they were on their personal way of working and participating (*"I am happy with how I got to participate and work during the forum"*). 65% of the respondents

expressed that they were pleased or very pleased how they managed to work and participate to the YPF process.

4.2 Learning experiences and outcomes

The learning outcomes and experienced impacts were scrutinized through scale questions, in which the respondents were asked to assess positive claims concerning the forum with a scale from one to five (1=not at all, 2=little, 3=somewhat, 4=significantly, 5=very significantly). The first claim was about the overall usefulness of the forum: “*The forum was useful to me*”. Two thirds of the respondents expressed that the forum was significantly or very significantly useful for them. 23% felt that it was somewhat useful, and 13% felt that the forum was just little useful for them. None felt that the participation was useless.

The Figure 1 illustrates how strongly the forum was experienced to contribute to the development of respondents’ *self-management practices, professional influencing, continuous personal development, career advancement, and professional identity*. Improvement of practices both personal and social as well as the respective skills, and personal developmental practices were the core aims of the forum.

Figure 1. Expressed and experienced YPF impacts 2017-22

It seems that the forum has been successful in promoting the skills and practices which were the actual topics of the forum – *self-management, professional influencing, continuous development*. Based on the questionnaire data the strongest impact was indicated on the professional influencing skills and practices as almost 80% of the respondents experienced significant, very significant or at least some impacts on their professional influencing skills and practices (“*The forum supported me in developing my own professional interaction and influence*”). The mildest impact was experienced on the career advancement. However, the career advancement was not in the actual focus of the forum. An interesting result is that the participation was experienced to strengthen the professional identity quite clearly despite the fact that the focus of the discussions and the whole forum was in social aspects of the engineering profession and practice, not in actual professional content. Almost 60% of the respondents felt

that there was a significant or very significant impact on professional identity (*“Participating in the forum has strengthened my professional identity”*).

All in all, the forum seemed to be a meaningful experience to the majority of the participants both personally and professionally. In the end of the inquiry the respondents were asked to assess how strongly would they recommend the forum to their colleagues and friends. The scale was from one to ten in which one represented the absolute no and ten absolute yes. The average was 7,9 when 79% of the respondents gave 7 or higher.

5 IMPACT FACTORS

The second topic we investigated was what factors of the forum were experienced as the most essential from a personal learning point of view. The respondents were asked to assess the impact factors with an open question in the inquiry: *“The forum consisted of workshops, personal assignments and peer group meetings, which formed a process that lasted about four months. What elements and components of the forum did you find most important for your own learning and benefit? Why?”* There were 66 responses to the question. The responses were categorized by the mentioned impact factors. Four categories were formed: *peer discussions, workshops, assignments, and the process as a whole.*

5.1 Peer groups

The vast number (over 80%) of the responses mentioned the peer discussions and peer groups as the most essential impact element of the forum. The peer group meetings between the workshops were mentioned to enable deeper conversations in which personal questions and experiences were shared in a safe environment. An important realisation mentioned was that all others had the similar questions and worries and that sharing those with others is meaningful as one respondent described: *“Peer group discussions helped me to realize that all have work related challenges and worries, and sharing those with others is fruitful. Our group met on free time which supported to build open and trusting connection within the group”*.

The peer meetings and sharing were mentioned to be essential forums and sessions for personal reflection and meaning making. The interactive and social reflection helped the respondents to clarify and expand their own thinking – why do I think like this? What are other possible ways of interpreting and thinking? Social reflections were experienced to be much more fruitful than just thinking and reflecting alone as one respondent described: *“Through peer discussions you got many view points and perspectives and not just your own. In peer discussions we generated a lot of new ideas and insights”*.

The peer groups were formed randomly and people did not know each other beforehand. Nevertheless, there were multiple comments on how the peer group was experienced as a safe and trusting environment to share personal thoughts and experiences, and discuss even uncertainties and worries as one respondent commented: *“Peer meetings between the workshops were very fruitful. The group*

formed a safe and trusting place to talk and share personal experiences". For most the peer group seemed to form trustful and helping relationship context which supported sense making, reflection, and personal development in a meaningful way. There were groups that continued to meet also after the forum.

An important aspect was also to hear and get practical tips about the methods and practices, and also share your own experiences. The peer group sessions and sharing was mentioned to support to develop professional self-confidence further. All in all the realization that I am not alone with all these questions seemed to ease the personal pressures to perform excellently all the time.

5.2 Workshops

The second impact factor mentioned was the workshops. The most forums had four three-hour workshops in the evening time from 5 pm to 8 pm. The workshops were participatory, including sections of lecturing, group discussions and exercises in pairs. The workshops were mentioned to form important moments for personal thinking and reflection. The most comments concerning the workshops were about the group discussions but the theoretical and conceptual content and introduced practices were also mentioned as value adding elements: *"The best for me were the practices and concepts presented in the workshops as well as the sharing of ideas"*. Some also mentioned the coaching exercises in pairs as an impactful course element. For some the workshop discussions remained vague compared to the discussions in the peer group. Before the Covid, the workshops set-up was face-to-face which enabled the participant to network and continue their discussions also during the breaks. In online time this opportunity was cut off. The online workshops were experienced as beneficial, however, three-hour intensive sessions after online workday was considered rather tiring and demanding by many participants.

5.3 Assignments

The personal assignments that were done between the workshops formed the third impact factor category mentioned by the respondents. There were three assignments altogether, which were connected to each other in a way that formed an integrated whole. Fourteen respondents mentioned the assignments as an essential element from their personal learning point of view. The most connected the assignments and various reflection discussions together as an impact factor: *"Assignments and peer discussions were important. Through these it was possible the process, think, and develop the issues further"*. The assignments enabled the participants to analyze and document their current situation, practices, thinking, relationships and work context, and later on in the workshops and peer discussions they were able to give deeper meanings and develop their thinking further. It was also mentioned that through the assignments, the participants produced a valuable documentation for themselves concerning their own development and practices.

5.4 The process as a whole

The fifth impact factor category mentioned by the respondents was the process as a whole. There were ten responses concerning the integrated and co-constituted impact of all the elements. One respondent described the impact very illustratively: *“I think that the most important from the learning point of view was the process as a whole. In the workshop the ideas and concepts were introduced and discussed which supported the accomplishment of the following assignment. Then the thoughts and insights from the assignment were shared with others in peer group meeting. The discussion continued in the following workshop and the ideas were shared cross the peer groups.”* Most of those who mentioned the forum as a whole to be the essential impact factor highlighted the integration and collective influence of different forum elements. There was only one respondent who stated boldly that he *“experienced the whole forum more or less as a waste of time”*.

6 DISCUSSION

This study is a work in progress. The YPF has been deemed a success by both the organizer TEK and the vast majority of the participants. Our data collection is still ongoing and this paper represents our first attempts to understand why and how the forum has been influential. According to our study, the participants in the YPF felt it enhanced their self-management practices, professional influencing, continuous personal development, and professional identity. It seems that the forum manages to produce impact on the essential working life and personal influencing skills in a sustained way.

The participants highlighted the peer discussions and opportunities to share their experiences, thoughts and insights as the most important part of the forum. Also the workshops and personal assignments got mentions as meaningful measures to support personal growth. Some participants saw that the process as a whole was what made it impactful. We argue that without the organized and facilitated process and individual analysis, and conceptual input the peer discussions would not have been so impactful. In our view, the experiences and impactfulness is most of all built through the confluence of different process elements.

The findings highlight strongly the social aspects of the learning process. One of our further directions in deepening our analysis is to look the forum as a *“temporary community of practice of learning”*. This would allow us to tap into the processual, dynamic and relational aspects of the learning process. In building a better understanding of how and why the forum was experienced impactful, we strive to contribute on how to help engineers better their collaboration, influencing, and personal development skills. To be sure, there are multiple ways to achieve these goals. However, we hope our experience will shed light on what kinds of interventions might work, and thus, provide additional understanding and concepts to (engineering) educators what makes soft skills development impactful.

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